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IMPACT OF FDI ON INDIAN RETAIL SECTOR

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Abstract

Liberalization of trade policies during the last one and half decade has led India to become an investment friendly country. Indian economy is basically an agro based as its 70% population engaged in the agriculture sector. When liberalization started in 1991, Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) was limited to only a few sectors like manufacturing, infrastructure etc. Change in FDI policy of India in 2012, which allowed investment in multi-brand retail stores, aviation sector and pension plan sectors, brought revolutionary changes in these sectors.

FDI plays an important role in India's growth dynamics. India being second most-populous country has immense scope for retail expansion as along with time urbanization and consumerism has also been increasing. Initially India was conservative regarding FDI; it imposed restriction on foreign companies to limit their share in equity capital of their Indian subsidiaries but over the time Government of India gradually liberalized foreign investment in various sectors. Recently in 2011 India permitted 100% FDI in single brand retail and in 2012, 51% FDI permitted in multi brand.

Keywords: Retail Sector, FDI, Opportunities and Challenges

Retail Sector In India

The organized sector is expected to grow to \$100 bn and account for 12-15% of retail sales by 2015(Singhal 1999). Retail sector is one of the biggest supports of the Indian economy and accounts for 15 percent of its GDP. The Indian retail market is estimated to be US\$ 450 billion and one of the top ten retail markets in the world by terms of economic value. India is one of the fastest emerging retail markets in the world, with 1.2 billion people. In simple words retailing is making the final product directly available to the final consumers of the product or a sale to the ultimate consumer. The Retail sector in India can be divided into two parts. One is organized and other is unorganized sector. Organized sector retailers are licensed retailers, those who have registered for sales tax, income tax etc. They are generally privately owned large businesses like Tanishq, Croma etc. on the other hand unorganized retail stores are like Kirana store, departmental store etc. which neither registered with any tax authorities nor with any other govt. department. Following are the three different forms through which organized retail trade in India is carried out.

Table 1

Mono/Exclusive/Single Brand Retail Shops	Multi brand Retail Shops	Convergence retail Outlets
Exclusive showrooms either owned or franchised out by the manufacturer. A complete range of all the products manufactured by the said manufacturer under one brand name	In these kinds of stores almost all brands of a single product are available. Customer has a very wide choice	These kinds of outlets have almost all products which a consumer may need.
Focus is on brand name	Focus is on nature of product	Focus is on diverse consumer needs
Nike show room etc.	Shoppers stop, Croma	Big bazaar etc.

Source: caclubindia.com

Table 2
Global Retail Development Index

2012 rank	Country	Market attractiveness (25%)	Country risk (25%)	Market saturation (25%)	Time pressure (25%)	GRDI Score	Change in Rank Compared to 2011
1	Brazil	100	85.4	48.2	61.6	73.8	0
2	Chile	86.6	100.0	17.4	57.1	65.3	0
3	China	53.4	72.6	29.3	100.0	63.8	+3
4	Uruguay	84.1	56.1	60.0	52.3	63.1	-1
5	India	31.0	66.7	57.6	87.9	60.8	-1
6	Georgia	27.0	68.7	92.6	54.0	60.6	NA
7	UAE	86.1	93.9	9.4	52.9	60.6	+1
8	Oman	69.3	98.3	17.4	50.4	58.9	NA
9	Mongolia	6.4	54.4	98.2	75.1	58.5	NA
10	Peru	43.8	55.5	62.9	67.2	57.4	-3

Source: IMF, World Bank, World Economic Forum

As per retail development index, India remained high potential market with accelerated growth of 15 to 20 % expected over next 5 years. Growth is supported by strong macro economic conditions, including a 6 to 7% rise in GDP, higher disposable income and rapid urbanization. Yet, while the overall retail market contributes to 14 % of India's GDP, organized retail penetration remained low, at 5 to 6 %, indicating room for growth. In January, 2012 FDI limit for single brand went upto 100% with a condition that sourcing must be 30% local. The changing FDI climate provides many large multibrands with the opportunity to enter and expand in Indian market. Groceries remained India's largest source of retail sale. Hypermarkets and supermarkets continue to be dominant. Private equity firms are more interested in retail sale. As many as 29 transactions were conducted in first half of 2011 in the retail consumer product space

Growth Drivers Of Indian Retail Sector:

- 1) Rising Income and increase in convergence of consumer taste and preferences.
- 2) Dual family Income.
- 3) Knowledge about different product through different medium like Internet, Television etc.
- 4) 47% of the India's population is under the age of 30. This category is driving the consumption.
- 5) Emergence of new retailing format.
- 6) Availability of Credit Facilities.

Opportunities for Retail Development in India

Retail marketing gets various opportunities to grow up in the Indian market. Not only retailing but Manufacturers as well as suppliers, and buyers have various opportunities, some of which are mentioned below

- 1) Provides visibility to Brands- Organized retail provides needed visibility to brands and a platform for customer interaction.
- 2) Urbanization- As large percentage of population has now been shifted to urban areas due to more job opportunities and more facilities for their children and family, they know the importance of brands and moreover they want everything under one roof, thus a single retail can catch more customers.
- 3) Nuclear Family- As the time passed away joint families came in a new form i.e. nuclear family. Again the income level of these nuclear families increases because both members started earning. This results into increased power of purchase and lack of time.
- 4) Plastic Revolution- Increased use of credit cards is in favor of retail marketing.
- 5) Indian Consumers- Organized retail stores put stress on proper infrastructure like well maintained building, air conditioning, trained employees, electronic machine, parking facilities and proper display of goods category wise. The customers feel good to see everything displayed in front of them which make purchase easier for them.

.6) High Availability of Jobs - There will be huge job opportunities in the country (in crores) as there will be opening of malls and store houses. The entry of modern retailers will expand the market creating large amount of additional jobs in retail. Opportunities will vary from ordinary workers to specialized officers.

Major Challenges For Retail Development In India

Organized retail in India is little over a decade old. It is largely an urban phenomenon and the pace of growth is still slow. Some of the reasons for this slow growth are: -

- 1) The Existence of Traditional KIRANA stores - The first and foremost challenge facing by the organized retail industry in India is competition from the unorganized sector.
- 2) Lack of Recognition as an Industry – Lack of recognition as an industry hampers the availability of finance to the existing and new players. This affects growth and expansion plans.
- 3) Lack of Infrastructural Facilities- Poor roads and transport facility hampers the development of food and grocery retail in India. The existing supermarkets and foods retailers have to invest a substantial amount of money and time in building a cold chain network
- 4) Price War-There is price war between different retail organizations. Each and every one is saying to provide goods at low cost and offers various promotional schemes. In such a case it is difficult to keep one's customers with oneself.

Suggestions For The Growth Of Retail Industry

FDI since 1991 has proved to be game changer for wide segments of Indian industry. FDI has changed quality, productivity, and production in areas where it has been allowed.

1. India needs to invest in infrastructure development if India wants to improve its retail industry.
2. India should increase the investment absorption capacity.
3. India should make FDI policies little bit more liberal so that it can face competition with other emerging economies.
4. Bureaucratic delays and various governmental approvals and clearances involving different ministries need to be fastened.
5. Restrictions on sector caps and entry route to sectors other than those of national importance need to be liberalized further and constant reviewing of policies must be done.
6. Government must ensure consistency of policy so as to improve the business and investor confidence
7. Licenses should be given on the basis of a population criterion, i.e. not more than X number of large format retail stores per Y population.
8. Adequate measures should be taken to ensure that Indian retail sector meets the international standards
9. Indian retail Industry should be backed with efficient supply-chain management
10. Specilized courses should be designed to train people for entering retail sector.

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